

BIOMECHANICAL FOUNDATIONS OF JUMPING TECHNIQUE**Islomova Marjona**

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ABSTRACT. Jumping into the water is a special system of movements in a strict sequence with certain requirements for the implementation of each element or phase. The leading factors in the performance of elements of diving are the characteristics of motor actions and interaction with a support, a partner or the aquatic environment. A high level of technical readiness in the performance of competitive elements is decisive in the conduct of sports activities.

KEY WORDS: diving, technique, elements, biomechanics, analysis, phases of jumps, FINA.

АННОТАЦИЯ. Прыжки в воду представляют собой особую систему движений строгой последовательности с определенными требованиями к выполнению каждого элемента или фазы. Ведущими факторами при выполнении элементов прыжков в воду выступают характеристики двигательных действий и взаимодействие с опорой, партнером или водной средой. Высокий уровень технической подготовленности при выполнении соревновательных элементов являются решающими при ведении спортивной деятельности.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: прыжки в воду, техника, элементы, биомеханика, анализ, фазы прыжков, FINA.

ANNOTATSIYA. Suvga sakrash - bu har bir element yoki fazani amalga oshirish uchun ma'lum talablarga ega bo'lgan qat'iy ketma-ketlikda harakatlarning maxsus tizimi. Suvga sakrash elementlarini bajarishda yetakchi omillar vosita harakatlarining xususiyatlari va tayanch, sherik yoki suv muhiti bilan o'zaro ta'sir qilishdir. Musobaqa

elementlarini bajarishda texnik tayyorgarlikning yuqori darajasi sport faoliyatidagi hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega.

KALIT SO‘ZLAR: suvga sakrash, texnika, elementlar, biomexanika, tahlil, suvga sakrash fazalari, FINA.

INTRODUCTION. Sport diving is the jumps performed by athletes in competition, listed in the official FINA tables and having a coefficient of difficulty. A jump into the water is a system of movements following one after another, providing repulsion and creation of body rotation around the transverse axis, flight, body control in flight and immersion in water upside down or head down [1].

The growth of sports results largely depends on the rationality and effectiveness of the technique of performing competitive exercises. The decisive factors in diving are the ability to assess and correct such characteristics of motor actions as repulsion from the support and the interaction of support links with it. To solve this problem, studies were conducted in the process of young athletes performing water jumps [2]

The aim of the research is to analyze the biomechanical foundations of each of the phases of diving from a tower.

METHODS. At competitions, sports jumps are performed from a rigid, fixed support - a tower, installed at a height of 1, 3, 5, 7.5 and 10 meters above the water surface.

In the course of the study, an analysis was made of the implementation of the main phases when performing jumps into the water from a tower. The study involved 10 beginner young athletes aged 8-9 years.

RESULTS. Let's consider each phase separately and analyze the biomechanical foundations of the technique for performing the main movements in each of them. Jumps performed from a place include: preparatory, repulsion, flight and immersion phases. Running jumps, in addition to the above phases, include a run-up phase.

The preparatory phase includes the starting position before the approach, the approach and the method of taking the starting position before the jump or before the run.

DISCUSSION. When performing jumps in the front stance, the approach to the starting position is performed in a natural step. If the jump is from a place, then, finishing the approach, the jumper puts one foot on the edge of the support, and then puts the second one on it (the toes should be flush with the edge of the tower). If the jump is from a run, then the athlete performs the same actions as in the first case, but puts his feet in the place where the run began (Fig. 1).

When performing jumps from the rear stance, the jumper approaches the edge of the support - just as when performing jumps from a place from the front stance; then he turns his back to the pond and stands on the front parts of the feet, the heels go beyond the edge of the support, but do not fall below its level (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Starting positions for diving.

After the approach, the athlete takes the starting position - the main stance: legs together, arms along the body, head straight, gaze directed forward, the muscles of the abdomen and buttocks should be tense. Straight arms rise up or to the sides or remain lowered along the body, while the hands are a natural extension of the forearms.

When performing jumps from a handstand (Fig. 1), the athlete approaches the edge of the tower, turns his back to the pool, bends over or crouches, puts his hands on

the edge of the tower, and then goes to the rack. Other options for entering the handstand are also possible. The starting position in the handstand must be held for 3 s, the body must be straightened (without bending in the lower back), the head is raised, the legs are closed, the knees are straightened, the toes are drawn.

The takeoff phase is aimed at performing a more effective repulsion and increasing the height of the departure. The run-up run on the tower consists of at least 4 steps, including the charge. Swoop - the final part of the run, is a jump with repulsion of one and the arrival on both legs at the end of the support.

From the position of biomechanics, a swoop is necessary in order to push off the support as much as possible. In addition, the coordination of movements with arms and legs has a significant effect on the height of repulsion. Therefore, the repulsion height during the attack should not be the maximum, but the optimal value.

In the attack, the athlete performs a repulsion with one leg while swinging the other. The fly leg is bent at the hip and knee joints - approximately to a right angle. At the top of the flight, the leg drops sharply down, while the body straightens, and the arms are held in a position to the sides up, maintaining balance and preparing to coordinate the movements of the arms and legs when pushing off from the edge of the board (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Run-attack when performing jumps from the tower from the front stance.

The repulsion phase is the main phase when performing jumps into the water. In the repulsion phase, the direction, the departure height necessary to perform the jumps, and the rotation of the body around the transverse axis are created.

Similar to repulsion from a solid support, when the athlete stands motionless on the support, the action of gravity and the reaction of the support is balanced. When performing repulsion from a place, movements should be performed with straightened arms, with a wide amplitude. Hands should move with acceleration from the bottom forward - up.

Having broken away from the support, by the action of internal (muscular) forces in flight, the athlete cannot change the flight trajectory, the amount of movement and the magnitude of the rotational impulse created during repulsion, however, he can control the speed of his rotation around the transverse axis (flip) and create rotation around the longitudinal axis (for screws).

It is most effective to perform the greatest range of movements that make up the jump figure in the upper part of the flight path - at the end of its ascending and beginning of its descending branches. At this moment, the inertial forces of repulsion and the forces of gravity are balanced, and the execution of movements requires less effort, which allows the athlete to show maximum speed qualities and make the jump easier to perform.

It is possible to control the speed of rotation around the transverse axis in flight by changing the length of the body, i.e., by taking positions of grouping or bending over. Having created the same rotational impulse during repulsion, the athlete, changing the length of the body, changes the moment of its inertia (Fig. 3). Thus, he can increase or decrease the speed of rotation of his body by 3.75-6.7 times. The minimum speed corresponds to the extended position of the body with arms raised above the head, and the maximum speed corresponds to the tuck position.

In flight, it is also possible to create rotation around the longitudinal axis of the body and control its speed. Rotation around the longitudinal axis of the body is created after the completion of repulsion or in its final stage.

Fig. 3. Change in the moment of inertia of the body when jumping into the water, depending on the position of the body in flight.

When creating body rotation around the longitudinal axis, it is necessary to distinguish two conditions under which it is fulfilled: 1) when the body does not have rotation around the transverse axis (training jumps - dismounts); 2) when the body has rotation around the transverse axis (sports jumps).

The speed of rotation around the longitudinal axis of the body depends on the speed of rotation along somersaults and the creation of body asymmetry. The rotation of the body around the longitudinal axis will occur in the direction of rotation of the body from the lowered hand to the raised one (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. The direction of occurrence of rotation around the longitudinal axis when creating asymmetry of the body in an unsupported position.

The athlete, having completed the jump, must plunge into the water at an angle close to 90 °, down with his feet or head, without splashing. In order to reduce splashing, the athlete must connect the hands in such a way that his head and shoulders can pass into the cavity created by them. Therefore, the simplest technique to help reduce splashing is the correct connection of the hands and the location of body parts relative to each other.

CONCLUSION. Biomechanical analysis of the kinematic and dynamic characteristics of the technique of performing the phases of jumps into the water made it possible to establish the motor composition of the studied movements, the nature of the activity of the support links. The features of the performance of repulsion in water jumps are determined, the motor composition is established and the differences in the functional activity of the support links during the performance of jumps are revealed.

An analysis of the technique for performing individual phases of jumps into the water showed that the timely technically competent mastering of these phases contributes to the qualitative performance of more technically complex jumps.

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